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Research Article

INFLUENCE OF PHARMACIST-LED EDUCATION ON NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE

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Abstract:

BACKGROUND: Non-alcoholic fatty liver is a condition characterized by excess lipid deposition in the hepatocytes of the liver without the excessive consumption of alcohol. The prevalence of NAFLD continues to increase in tandem with the rise of type 2 diabetes and obesity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: This is a prospective, cohort, and interventional study in which subjects were randomized into test and control groups by the block randomization method. The TyG index was calculated for all the patients to explore the relationship between the TyG index and NAFLD. The KAP questionnaire was administered to all the patients at baseline and three subsequent follow-ups. Patients in the test group received structured education at every follow-up on NAFLD, while the control group patients received only at the final follow-up.

RESULTS: A significant reduction in the TyG index values was observed in the test group compared to that of the control group ($p < 0.05$), indicating improved glycemic and lipid control following pharmacist-led education. KAP scores showed a marked improvement in the test group with a significant increase in knowledge and practice regarding NAFLD management. The TyG index demonstrated a positive correlation with the presence and severity of NAFLD. Patients who received regular pharmacist-led counselling showed better adherence to lifestyle modifications and dietary recommendations.

CONCLUSION: Pharmacist-led education significantly improves the understanding, management, and control of NAFLD by reducing the TyG index and enhancing patient compliance with lifestyle modifications.

KEYWORDS:

Fatty liver; non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, triglycerides-glucose index, patient counseling, diabetes, pharmacist intervention, lipid metabolism.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rheumatoid Arthritis is the most common Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is characterized by excessive liver fat depositions in people who drink little to no alcohol [1]. NAFLD pathogenesis ranges from basic steatosis to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), develops into fibrosis, and ultimately cirrhosis [5]. NAFLD is now regarded as the hepatic manifestation of metabolic syndrome. It is closely associated with obesity, insulin resistance, and type 2 diabetes mellitus [1].

About 25-30% of the population worldwide suffers from Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD), the most prevalent form of chronic liver disease [2]. In India, its prevalence is 38.6%, with urban people exhibiting a greater frequency [3].

Numerous research studies have been carried out in India that concentrate on liver enzymes or imaging-based diagnosis, Liver biopsies are invasive and expensive methods. The triglycerides-glucose (TyG) index is a simple and economical diagnostic tool used to detect NAFLD and insulin resistance among diabetic and obese patients. The TyG index, which is derived from fasting triglycerides and glucose levels [4].

The prevalence of NAFLD in India is rising because of low awareness of obesity, sedentary lifestyles, and insulin resistance. KAP studies can help understand public knowledge, attitudes, and practices, enabling effective educational and behavioral interventions by pharmacists [6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This is a prospective interventional study conducted in Mamata Academy of Medical Sciences [MAMA] Hospital, Bachupally, Hyderabad, India, over a period of 6 months. Patients in the MAMS meeting inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study using a block randomization technique to avoid selection bias.

Patients who are 18 years and older and have not yet been confirmed to have non-alcoholic fatty liver disease [NAFLD] and no prior intake of alcohol were included.

Patients who possess a history of severe liver disease or other long-term liver disorders and alcoholic consumption, pregnant women, and psychiatric patients were excluded.

A study data collection form was developed, and details like patient demographics, educational status, past medical history, family history, diet, marital status, smoking, and alcohol status were obtained.

All the enrolled patients were followed for 3 months from baseline with an interval of 30 days between the follow-ups. At every follow-up visit, CBG was recorded, that is fasting blood sugar [FBS], post-lunch blood sugar [PLBS], while HbA1C and Triglycerides are recorded at baseline and third follow-ups. The TyG index is calculated at baseline and the third follow-up.

The Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Questionnaire was administered at baseline and three subsequent follow-ups to assess the awareness of NAFLD. There are a total of 15 questions. This questionnaire was completed by the patient or patient attendant at a face-to-face interview with the investigator.

Test group patients received pharmacist education at every follow-up on lifestyle modifications, risk factors of NAFLD, while the control group patients received only at the final follow-up.

Statistical analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences [SPSS] was used to examine the data. Descriptive statistics were applied to identify the incidence rate and pharmacist influence in minimizing the risk of NAFLD. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to determine the total KAP scores among the test and control groups. Spearman correlation was applied to assess the correlation between the domains of various questionnaires and between the questionnaires.

RESULTS:

A total of 240 eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. These patients were randomized into a control and test group, 120 in each group. 56.66% and 44.33% were males and females, respectively, in the control group. While 45.83% and 54.16% were males and females, respectively, in the test group. The minimum age of the patients was 18 y and the maximum age of the patients was 78 y. The majority of patients in the control group fall under the age group of 46-60y, i.e., 53 [44.16%], and in the test group, the majority of them were from 46-60 y, i.e., 52 [43.33%]. The majority of the enrolled patients were educated in both the control and test groups of 72 [62.48%] and 71 [59.15%], respectively. Most of them completed graduation, i.e., 34 [28.33%] and 33 [27.50%] in the control and test group, respectively. In uneducated patients, i.e., 48 [40.00%] and 49 [40.83%] in the control and test group, respectively, who were farmers, daily wage workers, small business owners, housewives, and students.

The demographic details of the patients who had completed all the follow-ups are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Parameters	Control (n=120)	Test (n=120)
Age (years)	n %	n %
15-30	12 (10.0)	11 (9.16)
31-45	30 (25.0)	35 (29.16)
46-60	53 (44.16)	52 (43.33)
61-75	22 (18.33)	19 (15.83)
76-90	3 (2.5)	3 (2.50)
Gender		
Male	68 (56.66)	55 (45.83)
Female	52 (43.33)	65 (54.16)
Educational Qualification		
Uneducated	48 (40.00)	49 (40.83)
Primary School	17 (16.66)	10 (8.33)
Secondary School	10 (8.33)	17 (14.16)
Intermediate	11 (9.16)	11 (9.16)
Graduation	34 (28.33)	33 (27.50)
Current Employment Status		
Employed	34 (28.33)	33 (27.50)
Unemployed	66 (55.00)	70 (58.33)
Retired	20 (16.66)	17 (14.16)
Annual Income (INR)		
50,000-1,00,000	31 (25.83)	28 (23.33)
1,00,001-1,50,000	33 (27.50)	27 (22.50)
1,50,001-3,00,000	21 (17.50)	34 (28.33)
3,00,001-5,00,000	20 (16.67)	19 (15.83)
>5,00,000	15 (12.50)	12 (10.00)

The mean FBS and PLBS at the baseline follow-up in the control group were 119 mg/dl and 123 mg/dl, respectively. In the final follow-up, the mean FBS and PLBS were 123 mg/dl and 143 mg/dl. These values suggest that the glycaemic control did not improve significantly in the control group patients.

The mean FBS and PLBS at the baseline follow-up in the test group were 131 mg/dl and 193 mg/dl, respectively. In the final follow-up, the mean FBS and PLBS were 90 mg/dl and 148 mg/dl, which showed a significant improvement in the test group patients.

The HbA1C was repeated at the final follow-up to assess the impact of Pharmacist-led patient counseling on the diabetic profile of the enrolled patients. At the baseline, the mean HbA1C value was 6.88 in the control group patients and 6.35 in the test group patients. At the final follow-up, the mean HbA1C value was 4.98 among test group patients and 5.76 in the control group patients, which showed remarkable improvement in the test group.

The mean triglyceride value at the baseline follow-up was 178 mg/dl in the test group and 170 mg/dl in the control group. At the final follow-up, the mean triglyceride value was 99 mg/dl in the test group and 143 mg/dl in the control group.

At the baseline, the mean TyG index was 4.92 in the test group and 4.89 in the control group. At the end of the final follow-up, the mean TyG index value was 4.38 in the test group and 4.83 in the control group, which showed significant improvement among the patients in the test group.

The KAP score from the baseline to final follow-up in the test group was significantly improved compared to the control group.

DISCUSSION:

The study assessed the impact of pharmacist-led education in managing Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD) risk using the Triglyceride-Glucose (TyG) index. Conducted in a tertiary care teaching hospital, it evaluated demographic factors, lifestyle behaviors, and Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) levels in both test and control groups. Middle-aged individuals, particularly males, were the most affected. A notable proportion of the test group were smokers and had intermediate-level education, whereas the control group had a higher percentage of non-smokers and individuals with primary education. Post-intervention, the test group showed significant improvements in TyG index (from 4.92 to 4.38), HbA1C levels (from 7.29% to 4.98%), and triglycerides (from 178 mg/dL to 99 mg/dL). Additionally, KAP scores in the test group increased from 9.39 to 22.99, indicating improved awareness and lifestyle adherence. The intervention confirmed that pharmacist-led counseling positively influences NAFLD management by enhancing patient understanding and encouraging behavioral changes. However, the study had limitations, including a relatively small sample size, no follow-up diagnostic imaging, and the exclusion of confounding factors like stress and environmental influences. Future studies should integrate imaging techniques, biomarker assessments, and extended follow-up periods to evaluate the TyG index's predictive validity. The study underscores the importance of early risk identification, pharmacist involvement, and consistent monitoring in reducing NAFLD incidence and associated cardiovascular complications. Expanding the sample size and incorporating more robust statistical methods and diagnostic tools can further validate these findings and improve intervention outcomes.

CONCLUSION:

Pharmacist-led education significantly improved KAP scores and reduced NAFLD risk using the TyG index. The test group showed notable reductions in TyG, HbA1C, and triglycerides. The study emphasizes early risk detection and lifestyle modification through counselling, though further research with diagnostic imaging and broader sampling is recommended.

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